

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation report (acceptance note) for **TEBT-2025-0018**

Submission information table

Submission Title	AI-assisted Automation for Converting Historical Documents into Structured Database: A Feasibility Study of Environmental Application in Michigan
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0018
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration of Interests	The editor is not aware of any conflicts of interest that could compromise their handling of this submission.
Number of Reviewers	1 editor, 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Research Article ▾
Preregistration Level	N/A (Not Applicable) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17804938
Report Number	3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Date	1 Jul 2026
Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of the data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies. Prophy.ai was used to help identify peer-reviewers for the manuscript.
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Explanation of Acceptance Decision

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript presents a feasibility study of an AI pipeline for converting legacy physical environmental documentation into machine-readable data, focusing on a specific problem area and context without attempting to investigate the generalisability or scalability of the pipeline. This is legitimate given the resources the authors were working with, making the manuscript a modest but nonetheless useful contribution to the literature.

Unfortunately, the reviewer recommending major revisions was not available to check the revised manuscript. I therefore reviewed the manuscript myself. While I was expecting quite substantial revisions after peer-review, the authors responded to reviewer comments without making extensive changes to the manuscript. The authors argued that, because this is a feasibility study without a goal of measuring performance or generalisability of the pipeline, detailed performance metrics, full reporting of prompts, and other such information, may be desirable but is not essential. I agree.

I have also not been strict on requiring pipeline code and supporting documentation, as this appears to be held by the NIEHS until specific institutional procedures have been applied. This is not ideal but, given some of the challenges around working with US Federal institutions at the present time, and that some data can anyway only be made available on request for ethical reasons, we will allow the authors to make all data available on request and encourage them to upload what they can to the Zenodo record of their preprint once it has been released by the funder.

Overall, I conclude that the revisions the authors have made are sufficient, and I am therefore pleased to accept the manuscript for publication.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript was accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 2 rounds of revision (1 round responding to editorial evaluation and 1 round responding to peer-review evaluation). The evaluation reports for the manuscript can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1802151>. Preprint versions of the manuscript and author responses to comments in the evaluation reports can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17804938>.

